

IMPLEMENTING TOLERANCE IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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ABSTRACT

In communication, aggression can lead to contradictions, failure of communication, but tolerance is one of the most effective means to avoid aggression and guarantee the continuation of communication. The main content of this study is to analyze problems caused by verbal aggression on communication, show the role and approaches of tolerance in the regulation of linguistic means and situations.

Keywords: *Tolerance, aggression, Aggressiveness, Communication, Cultural linguistics, Linguistic barrier, Linguistic situation.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Communication is a key part of modern life, and people rely on it to exchange information, achieve their goals and maintain relationships. Communication depends on both interpersonal and non-personal factors. For example, in family life, communication takes place in the form of talking with other family members or discussing important matters with relatives. In school life, communication takes place when teachers give lectures to students or discuss lessons with classmates. When you make official documents such as government documents or bills, you use communication to express your feelings while making requests or giving feedbacks. In the process of forming communication, various factors affect its effectiveness and results: the expressive means used by one person (words), the communicative principles used by that person (e.g., truthfulness), other factors like cultural background etc.

2. Social, cultural, and personal factors influence communication.

As a social development organization of speech, language learning also has a linguistic level, the human personality, cultural differences, social psychology and others. In addition to linguistic personality and culture, language learning also focuses on problems associated with interaction between the addresser and the addressee in communication practice in order to better understand the real purpose and basis for the use of appropriate expressive methods.

Communication is a joint specificity of motives, goals, plans and strategies which depend on ways of thinking and position both parties have regarding personal education levels, religious and cultural differences in the community. Therefore study of communicative methods also needs to focus on functions of speech.

The scientist Sidorov views speech as an impelled need for universal sign coordination, correlated with reality (linguistic and non-linguistic), expedient, internal or internal and external activity of the individual, performed in the form of speech-psychological actions and operations using the sign resources of the language system based on the communicative ability and experience of its implementation [9].

The communicative approach to language focuses on the study of the final result—the effect of linguistic communication—and can be called pragmatics. In this approach, linguistics is considered to be an integral characteristic in terms of mutual influence among interlocutors in the process of communication [8]. The communicative-pragmatic approach involves taking into account significant components of language units, which are associated with a person who uses language as a tool of communication and makes his choice to achieve tasks set when orienting in a situation as a whole, social characteristics of the addressee and so on [13].

As defined in "Stylistic Encyclopedic Dictionary of Russian Language", communication is the expression of text by means of linguistic interaction to communicate, understood as the ratio of semantic roles as given the reactions of the recipient (including the second I), as well as explication in the text of signs actually dialogue.

3. Correlation between linguistic aggressiveness and tolerance

In negotiations, tolerance is manifested in two ways: verbal aggression and linguistic tolerance.

Negative cultural faux pas are not easily forgiven, and they make the most negative impression. Overcoming the cultural barrier is impossible without a tolerant perception of reality, which is manifested in the loyal and friendly attitude of at least one of the communicants to another. Tolerant perception in negotiations is manifested in linguistic tolerance, which is an essential component of linguistic competence.

Linguistic competence helps to achieve optimal results in dialogues, as often during conflicts there are situations caused by the fact that "parties defend their positions in every possible way and force their opponent to make concessions. At the same time, they often resort to false or one-sided arguments." [11]. According to Shcherbinina, such situations are a prerequisite for the emergence of discontent and conflict which hinders the implementation of important tasks: communication has a destructive effect on consciousness of participants in communication, makes it difficult to fully exchange information, significantly reduces the possibility of mutual understanding of communicants, blocks the development of a common strategy of interaction." [16].

Barod and Richardson defined aggression as any form of behavior aimed at insulting or harming another living being who does not want such treatment [3].

Vakhrushev noted that "there are different strategies for overcoming verbal aggression: reflection, empathy and tolerance. And it is tolerance, or rather, its linguistic refraction, that is the most successful and effective strategy for overcoming verbal aggression" [4].

5. Conclusion

The study of linguistic aggressiveness and tolerance in communication is a topical topic. Mastering linguistic tolerance helps to solve the problem of verbal aggression in communication, reduce the level of discourse, reduce the negative impact of discourse, express a tolerant attitude to the object, and ultimately achieve a communicative

intention. The study of linguistic tolerance and verbal aggressiveness complements existing principles and standards for intercultural communication education; it has practical significance in cross-cultural communication training for professionals as well as theoretical significance in aspect language culturology.

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